

A ROS-based framework to boost the manipulation tasks programming and execution

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Abstract—This paper introduces a robotic manipulation framework for the programming and execution of manipulation tasks. The framework is based on the ROS platform and provides advanced motion planning and control functionalities to relieve the upper control layers from the management of low-level functionalities and the task geometrical information. The framework is modular with respect to motion planning and control algorithms and is able to deal with dynamically updated scenes. Moreover, it provides an interface through which high-level actions can be implemented and executed automatically. Examples of some basic actions, such as *go to*, *pick*, *place*, are also available and ready to use.

Keywords—Robotic manipulation, robot programming, industrial robots, motion planning, action planning.

Figure 1. Manipulation framework layers description.

I. INTRODUCTION

The definition of “*robotic manipulation*” tends to change according to the field of the applications [1]. Over the years, robotic manipulation has referred to a broad combination of motion planning and motion control of a robotic arm, equipped by a proper grasping tool, to execute a predefined task where it is required to interact with objects in the surrounding environment [2]. In this regard, euRobotics association, through the strategic research agenda [3], defined *manipulation* as “*the function of utilising the characteristics of a grasped object to achieve a task*”.

Task management is, in general, demanded by a high-level “*task planner*”, that supervises the overall process working at an abstract level, frequently supported by AI algorithms [4]. The hierarchical approach to task planning is the most common one where the task planner is involved in a massive number of operations that can be coded and automatized at a different level by acting as a decision maker and as an executor able to: (i) decompose a complex task into single actions, (ii) plan a feasible sequence of actions and (iii) supervise their executions.

The *MoveIt!* library [5] provides a package able to perform pick&place tasks but with limited features and a rigid definition of the manipulation pipeline. Indeed, it considers a unique grasping pose of a unique object at a time, allowing the path planning for the approaching movement, the reaching of the picking or grasping pose, and the leaving movements.

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Recently, [6] has merged *MoveIt!* with a framework that composes tasks taking into account the planning context.

A. Motivation and contribution

For a given manipulation task, this work aims to present a manipulation framework able to:

- (i) process manipulation actions (such as pick, place, pick&place, screw, packing, etc...) with a certain level of autonomy relieving the task planner from the management and the execution of simple actions;
- (ii) handle the kinematic model of the robotic system (arm + grasping system) being able to compute forward and inverse kinematics;
- (iii) embed motion planning functionalities to generate collision-free trajectories for a given planning scene and a given robotic system in a planning environment that can dynamically change;
- (iv) be as modular as possible to be easily extended by the user with custom actions.

A detailed description of the framework can be found in [7].

II. FRAMEWORK MODULES

The following nomenclature will be used: a **Task** is the final goal to be reached by the robotic system represented by a group of **Actions**. An **Action** is a sequence of elementary movements made by the robotic system. A **Skill** is the elementary movement executed by the robotic system, a group of **Skills** forms an **Action**.

The framework architecture is shown in Figure 1, where:

- the *Locations Manager* layer (colored in green) has in charge the management of the geometrical information

Figure 2. Manipulation framework external dependencies.

and the motion planning. The module can dynamically add and remove *Locations*. By embedding a planning pipeline it allows the use of different motion planners, planning scene and a kinematics module.

- the *Skills Manager* layer (colored in orange) manages the trajectory execution, the robot controllers and the manipulation tools. The module allows loading/unloading of the robot controllers according to the running *Skill*. The module can start and monitor the execution of the trajectories planned by the *Locations Manager* and enables the control of the tool required by the *Action*.
- the *Actions Manager* layer (colored in blue) deals with the *Actions* decomposition and the *Skills* execution. This module supervises the execution of each single *Action*.

III. IMPLEMENTATION

The manipulation framework was developed as a C++ library based on ROS [8]. The external libraries (see Figure 2) used to develop the modules are:

- *MoveIt!* [5] to exploit its planning pipeline and its planning scene. Thanks to the plugins mechanism provided by ROS, the motion planners (such as OMPL, CHOMP, STOMP) can be dynamically loaded. The planning scene enables the collision checking, where collision detectors can be also loaded as plugins. The manipulated objects with the environment are evaluated by the motion planner.
- *RosDyn* [9] to compute inverse kinematics with high computational performance.
- *cnr_ros_control* [10], an extension of standard ROS control architecture [11], that allows to seamlessly start/stop ROS controllers, with the main difference that complex control architecture, with multiple nested controller, can be defined and loaded. The robot controllers can also be set online and smoothly changed during the execution of different *Skills*. The dynamic change of controllers provides a high degree of flexibility to the manipulation framework being able to adapt the robot behavior based on the specific *Skill* under execution.

A Human Machine Interface (HMI) was developed to further simplify the usage of the package also for the users that are not familiar with ROS.

The *manipulation* framework is an open source library available in the public repository [12]. Examples about the usage of the framework are also available at [13].

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The paper introduced a manipulation framework designed to address manipulation tasks. The framework is designed to have a certain level of autonomy in processing *Actions* and *Skills* relieving the task planners from the management of low level functionalities as the robotic system motion planning and motion control and objects geometrical information. The robot controllers can be started/stopped on the base of the required *Skills*. Future activities will measure the programming time reduction by using the manipulation framework and its HMI compared to the standard programming tools such as the definition of the robot part-program through the use of the robot teach pendant. The integration with symbolic task planners is also an ongoing activity [14].

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